

Bilateral Femoral Shaft Fractures with Ipsilateral and Delayed Contralateral Femoral Neck Fractures following High-Energy Trauma: A Diagnostic and Management Challenge

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Abstract

High-energy blunt trauma frequently results in complex orthopedic injuries, including bilateral femoral shaft fractures. These injuries are occasionally associated with concomitant femoral neck fractures, which can be radiographically occult and clinically challenging to diagnose. We report the case of a 53-year-old male who sustained bilateral comminuted femoral shaft fractures and an ipsilateral (right-sided) femoral neck fracture following a high-velocity motor vehicle collision. A contralateral (left-sided) femoral neck fracture, initially missed on both preoperative imaging and intraoperative assessment, was identified on postoperative radiographs. This case underscores the diagnostic difficulty of femoral neck fractures in the setting of polytrauma and bilateral femoral shaft injuries, emphasizing the importance of vigilant imaging review, intraoperative fluoroscopy, and postoperative reassessment.

Introduction

Bilateral femoral shaft fractures are rare and almost exclusively the result of high-energy mechanisms, such as motor vehicle collisions. The incidence of ipsilateral femoral neck fractures in patients with femoral shaft fractures ranges from 1% to 9%, with the risk markedly increasing in the context of polytrauma. Concomitant bilateral femoral neck fractures in this setting are exceedingly rare and may be radiographically occult at presentation. Missed femoral neck fractures may lead to significant morbidity due to risks of avascular necrosis (AVN), non-union, and impaired functional outcomes.

This case report presents the diagnostic and operative challenges associated with a delayed diagnosis of a left femoral neck fracture in a patient who presented with bilateral comminuted femoral shaft fractures and an initially identified right femoral neck fracture.

Case Presentation

A 53-year-old male (BMI: 34.6; weight: 125 kg; height: 190 cm), with a past medical history of hypertension, presented to the Emergency Department via emergency medical services following a high-speed motor vehicle collision. He was the restrained driver, with airbag deployment. There was no reported loss of

consciousness or signs of head trauma.

Fig 1: Left femur fracture:

Fig 2: Right femur fracture :

Fig 3: CT pelvic:

Fig 4: Postoperative left femur Fixation, Retrograde femur nail:

Fig 5: Postoperative right femur Fixation TFNA:

Fig 6: Postoperative CT left hip:

Fig 7: 2nd Postoperative left femur neck fracture Fixation with DHS:

Primary Survey and Initial Assessment

The patient was hemodynamically borderline on arrival (BP: 97/58 mmHg), with prompt improvement following fluid resuscitation (BP stabilized to 135/83 mmHg). He was alert and oriented, reporting bilateral thigh pain as the predominant complaint. Physical examination revealed gross deformity of both mid-thighs, an open laceration over the right knee, and a superficial soft tissue injury in the left inguinal region. Neurovascular examination of the lower extremities was unremarkable. No signs of compartment syndrome were present.

Initial Imaging and Laboratory Workup

A trauma protocol whole-body CT scan (CT pan-scan) revealed:

Bilateral comminuted femoral diaphyseal fractures

Right-sided basicervical femoral neck fracture

Grade II hepatic contusion

Right first rib fracture

Initial hemoglobin was 136 g/L, decreasing to 122 g/L preoperatively; one unit of packed red blood cells

(PRBCs) was transfused. The radiological assessment was reportedly negative for any left femoral neck pathology.

Surgical Management

Operative Planning (Day 1 Post-Admission)

Given the patient's soft tissue injuries and bilateral femoral fractures, a staged operative plan was adopted. The patient was optimized for surgery after multidisciplinary input from the trauma and anesthesia teams.

Procedures Performed (Day 1):

Debridement and closure of the right knee laceration and left inguinal wound.

Left Femur: Retrograde intramedullary nailing (IMN) of the femoral shaft to avoid traversing the inguinal wound.

Right Femur: Cephalomedullary nailing using a Trochanteric Fixation Nail Advanced (TFNA) for the femoral shaft and basicervical neck fracture, augmented with two 6.5 mm anti-rotation cannulated screws.

Intraoperative fluoroscopy focused on both the shaft and the femoral neck regions. No abnormalities were noted in the contralateral (left) femoral neck at this stage.

Postoperative Course

Postoperative Day 2: Unexpected Finding

Routine postoperative radiographs revealed a previously unrecognized displaced left femoral neck fracture. A retrospective review of the initial CT scan and intraoperative imaging again failed to demonstrate any clear signs of this fracture.

Return to Theatre (Post-op Day 2):

The patient was returned to the operating room urgently for internal fixation of the newly diagnosed left femoral neck fracture using a Dynamic Hip Screw (DHS) construct.

Complications and Considerations

Preoperative:

Hemodynamic instability (likely secondary to hemorrhage), successfully managed.

Anemia requiring transfusion.

Intraoperative:

Complexity of surgical positioning and planning due to bilateral injuries.

Missed diagnosis of occult left femoral neck fracture despite imaging and intraoperative screening.

Postoperative:

Increased morbidity due to a second operative intervention.

Elevated risk of avascular necrosis (AVN) and non-union of the femoral neck.

Risk of surgical site infection (open wounds over the right knee and left groin).

High risk of thromboembolic events given polytrauma status, obesity, and reduced mobility.

Discussion

This case illustrates a rare constellation of injuries involving bilateral femoral shaft fractures, an ipsilateral (right) femoral neck fracture, and a delayed presentation of a contralateral (left) femoral neck fracture. The delayed diagnosis may be attributable to the radiographically occult nature of the fracture, intraoperative positioning constraints, and limitations in standard trauma CT resolution.

The development of the left femoral neck fracture post-fixation raises the possibility of an initially occult or stress-induced fracture becoming displaced secondary to biomechanical changes after shaft fixation. This phenomenon has been described in literature, where femoral shaft stabilization alters force distribution, potentially precipitating displacement of previously stable or non-displaced neck fractures.

Imaging Recommendations:

Thin-slice (≤ 2 mm) axial CT scans with coronal and sagittal reformats of the femoral neck should be standard in cases of femoral shaft fractures from high-energy trauma.

Intraoperative fluoroscopic evaluation must include dedicated anteroposterior and lateral views of both hips before and after shaft fixation.

When suspicion is high, some authors advocate for prophylactic screw fixation of the femoral neck.

Conclusion

This case highlights the need for a high index of suspicion for associated femoral neck fractures in the setting of femoral shaft injuries, particularly in polytrauma patients. Delayed diagnosis of such fractures can significantly affect patient outcomes. Rigorous preoperative imaging, intraoperative vigilance, and postoperative reassessment are vital to identifying and managing these injuries appropriately.

Learning Points

Always evaluate for ipsilateral and contralateral femoral neck fractures in the context of femoral shaft fractures.

Employ high-resolution CT with multiplanar reconstructions to assess for occult femoral neck injuries.

Intraoperative fluoroscopy should include targeted hip views even when shaft fixation is the primary procedure.

Occult femoral neck fractures may manifest post-fixation; postoperative imaging should not be omitted.

A multidisciplinary and staged surgical approach is often necessary in polytrauma patients to optimize outcomes.

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